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Research Article

**TEMPORALITY AND SOCIO-CULTURAL ADAPTATION
AMONG STUDENTS OF KING EDWARD MEDICAL
UNIVERSITY**¹Dr. Humera Javed, ²Dr. Yusra Arooj, ³Dr. Hira Khalid¹Mayo Hospital Lahore²House Officer Mayo Hospital Lahore³Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Abstract:**

A quantitative, analytical study was performed to analyze the level of socio-cultural adaptation among the students of King Edward Medical University. Intersocio-cultural adaptation means adopting the cultural norms and social habits and behavior of the fellow students / colleagues while living in the same environment at the same point in time in order to cope up with the challenges of environment. The aim was to find out level of adaptation in two separate categories of students with respect to time they have spent in same environment and compare the values to check significant difference. The sampling technique used was cluster probability sampling. 50 students from each category (1st year and 4th year MBBS) were chosen and were asked to fill in the questionnaire provided, which was based on Socio-cultural Adaptation Scale-Revised (SCAS-R). The data was collected within a week and SPSS analysis system was used to get the results.

According to the results, there was no significant difference in the adaptation of students from both categories as the P-value was >0.05. Even the effect modifiers (gender and mother's occupation) did not show significant adaptation according to P-value. Mean values, however, showed a slightly raised level of adaptation in males as compared to females. These findings were contrary to our expectations because of limited time and inevitable human errors. There is still a need, however, to promote diversity and cultural sensitivity. There should be an ease of access to every facility the institute provides, for everyone equally, so that none suffers because of difference in social and cultural backgrounds.

Keywords: *inter-socio-cultural, environment, adaptation, behavior, challenges.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Socio-cultural adaptation is a big issue for the students when they start their professional careers in a new environment. Often these problems are overlooked and ignored, these all might have an effect on the overall working capacity and academic performance as well as it can have an effect on the personality of individuals as well. Medical colleges and boarding schools should increase their efforts by providing more opportunities to promote social and cultural interaction among students from different areas. This study provides an idea of how socio-cultural adaptation affects the students of King Edward Medical University, in terms of unique comparison of socio-cultural adaptation among two years and then effect of time and other variables on socio-cultural adaptation and whether the universities are capable of coping with these stresses of students. This understanding can serve as a guidance for administration staff, college authorities and faculty to adequately cope with the challenges that are faced by. While the limitations restrict one from drawing extensive conclusions, some insight is provided into student's behavior and adaptation in medical college relative to levels of socio-cultural adaptation.

These findings suggest that higher education professionals should also place an emphasis on ensuring that currently enrolled students are provided quality academic and social experience to prevent them from facing high levels of stress and difficulty adapting to the campus and leading to satisfied students. Unsatisfied students often are not retained or result in having lower academic success; therefore, aiding students is quite important to satisfied students. In addition, current research findings reveal that students who are socially and culturally more satisfied are more active and have more positive effect not only on their institutions' reputation but they also have a good and positive role in the development of country and the development of man-kind as well.

METHODOLOGY:

An analytical study was conducted to measure and analyze level of acculturative stress and level of socio-cultural adaptation in students of King Edward Medical University that were present in the campus during this study. A sample size of total 101 students was obtained which included both male and female. A total of 51 (10 males and 41 females) students from first year and 50 students (12 males, 38 females) from 4th year participated in this study. Randomized sampling technique was used and students from fourth year and first year were included in the sample while the students of third year, second year and final year were excluded. All those who

participated were explained about the objectives and were informed clearly that participation in it was voluntary and they had the right to remain anonymous.

A pre-tested standard questionnaire was used for data collection. Out of both classes 51% people from first year and 50% from fourth year responded to the research. Most of them were females 80.3% from first year and 76% from fourth year. It consisted of two parts: the first part dealt with socio-demographic data, variables pertaining to demographic profile and personal factors such as age, gender, parents' education level, parents' occupation. The second part constituted as socio-cultural adaptation questionnaire (ANNEXURE 1) that was based on the revised version of socio-cultural adaptation scale- (SCAS-R). The scale was designed to see the extent of socio-cultural adaptation by students in terms of daily and academic life using SCAS-R that consisted of 21 items to which participants responded to all questions using a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1="Not at all Competent" to 5="Extremely Competent." Scores obtained from the scale were perceptions about the social and cultural difficulties faced. Five sub-scales were identified that included 7 items with

inter personal communication, 4 items in academic / work performance, 4 regarding personal interests and community involvement, 4 referring to ecological adaptation, and 2 referring to one's language proficiency while living in a different culture. The mean scores ranged from 1 to 5, with lower scores indicating greater social difficulties and socio-cultural adaptation problems; higher scores represent greater competency in a new cultural environment. Scores were calculated by obtaining the mean score for individual items. The research incorporated the comparison of these sub-scales in first year and fourth year to see socio-cultural adaptation with time in new environment. These results were also compared between male and female and those who studied in English medium vs. other mediums. Data was collected by an online survey that took a period of two months approx (w.e.f. 11 June -15 August). Questionnaire was uploaded on social website through Google forms. Online survey was completed by 101 students of both years; set and items were coded using SPSS software to determine whether any relationship existed between the levels of sociocultural adaptation and other factors. A total score of 21 using SCAS-R of adaptation was devised as an outcome variable. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and percentages) were used for summarizing the outcome variables.

RESULTS:

A brief demographic profile accompanied these instruments. The demographic survey asked respondents the following information: gender, age, previous school / college, father's and mother's occupation. Questionnaire respondents were

predominantly female (79.5%), with a mean age of 20 years. Respondents were asked whether they had studied in government or private institute to analyze how good they are at understanding and writing new things in English.

OBSERVATIONS	FIRSTYEAR			FOURTHYEAR			Frequ Ency	per cent	CUMUL ATIVE PERCE NT
	frequ ency	per cent	Cumu lative perce nt	Frequ Ency	per cent	Cumu lative frequ ency			
MALE	10	19.6	19.6	12	24.0	24.0	12	24.0	24.0
FEAMLE	51	80.4	100	38	76.0	100.0	38	76.0	100.0
PRIV SCHOOL	32	62.7	72.5	25	50.0	50.0			
GOV SCHOOL	9	17.6	90.2	40	28.0	78.0			
SEMI- GOVT	5	9.8	100	11	22.0	100.0			
FATHER GOVT EMPLOY EE	26	51.0	51.0	19	38.0	38.0			
FATHER OCCUPA TION PRIVATE	25	49.0	100.0	31	62.0	100.0			
MOTHER HOUSEW IFE	41	80.4	80.4	42	84.0	84.0			
MOTHER	10	19.6	100	8	16.0	100.0			
WORKIN G	6			0					

The literature review suggested that students' acculturation experiences are influenced by multiple factors, which include student's socio cultural adaptation to a new culture. The particular goal of the study was to investigate sociocultural adaptation over the years, including the five sub scales of sociocultural adaptation in fourth year and the five sub scales of socio-cultural adaptation in first year so as to understand that fourth year students adapt well to socio-cultural differences in comparison of first year students on socio-cultural adaptation. According

to this survey first subgroup of interpersonal communication had a small difference of SD from mean that supported our hypothesis. No significant difference existed in mean so therefore the four sub groups when they were compared between two years. But when the total sum of sub groups was conducted fourth year has little higher mean than first year thus supporting our hypothesis. although SD of both groups was a little higher than a difference of both means it was not that significantly higher.

Group Statistics					
	class/MBBSyear	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Std.ErrorMean
Interpersonal	FirstYear	51	23.18	3.907	.547
	FourthYear	50	24.66	4.034	.570
Communication	FirstYear	51	13.35	1.842	.258
	FourthYear	50	13.28	2.195	.310
Academicperformance	FirstYear	51	11.65	2.704	.379
	FourthYear	50	12.26	2.827	.400
Personal interest and communityinvolvement	FirstYear	51	11.63	2.280	.319
	FourthYear	50	12.34	2.512	.355
Ecologicaladaptation	FirstYear	51	7.10	1.700	.238
	FourthYear	50	6.92	1.563	.221
Languageproficiency	FirstYear	51	66.9020	8.05296	1.12764
	FourthYear	50	69.4600	10.01470	1.41629
total					

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